

Studies on Adsorption of Rhodamine B on Silica Gel

M. L. MIRZA*, N. YASMIN, J. IQBAL and A. WADOOD

Chemistry Department, Islamia University, Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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Adsorption behaviour of rhodamine B from aqueous, alcoholic and from basic solutions have been investigated over silica gel. The modes of adsorption observed were namely S, L and H type isotherms, and the nature of adsorption have been explained. Sodium hydroxide strongly inhibits the extent of adsorption. Kinetics of adsorption reveals two types of adsorption processes.

ONLY a few reports are available on rhodamine adsorption on finely divided solids. Giles *et al.*¹ studied the adsorption of cationic dyes including rhodamine B over chromatographic alumina. The alkaline chromatographic alumina readily adsorbed rhodamine molecules. The rate of adsorption was very high and rhodamine B was found to be completely desorbed by water. Gestko² studied the adsorption and luminescence spectra of rhodamine B over cadmium sulphide crystals. The orientation of the adsorbed molecules on cadmium sulphide crystal was determined for various adsorption regions.

Experimental

Three differently treated samples of silica gel (E. Merck) were tested. The procedure of their preparation and activation has been described elsewhere³. In a few studies, the adsorbent was impregnated in 0.1N NaOH solution for 2 h, dried (24 h) in the oven at 100° followed by activation at 450° for 5 h. The adsorbents were stored in a desiccator (CaCl₂) to avoid moisture. Rhodamine B (C.I. 45170; E. Merck, C.P.) was used without further purification. All other chemicals were AnalaR grade. The stock solution of rhodamine B (50 ppm) was prepared after every couple of weeks to minimise aggregation of the dye molecules in solutions. The adsorption procedure was similar as described earlier³. Weighed quantities of silica (0.5 g) were immersed in the dye solutions in 25 ml conical flasks. The flasks were tumbled for ~1 h, then left under thermostating conditions for 24 h. The amount of dye adsorbed was measured spectrophotometrically. The plots of absorbance against concentrations of dye solution, obeyed the Beer-Lambert law. Plots of log (concentration) against time gave a first order kinetic plot. The kinetics of adsorption was studied by taking silica (0.5 g) in a series of conical flasks followed by addition of 25 ml (5 ppm) dye solution. After specific intervals of time, portions of dye solutions were taken out and the concentration was determined spectrophotometrically, from which the amount of dye retained by silica was calculated (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Kinetics of rhodamine B adsorption from: (●) aqueous, (●) alcoholic, and (○) NaOH-treated silica gel.

Results and Discussion

Giles *et al.*⁴ classified four kinds of adsorption behaviours of solute from dilute solutions, viz. H, L, S and C type adsorption isotherms. The H-type refers to high affinity of solute adsorption onto the adsorbent. The L-type represents 'flatwise' adsorption of solute molecules oriented parallel to the surface. The S-type isotherm indicates 'end-on' adsorption and the surface layer is vertical to the substrate. The C-type adsorption signifies the constant partition of the solute between the surface layer and the solution phase. In the present investigations, rhodamine B follows H, L and S type isotherms (Fig. 2). The S-type behaviour was found in adsorption from aqueous solutions of the dye, which shows that rhodamine B is adsorbed as end-on (vertical to the surface), monolayer, mono-disperse and with some ionic micelles formation followed by multilayer adsorption. The adsorption

Fig. 2. Adsorption of rhodamine B from: (●) aqueous (S-type), (●) alcoholic (L-type), and (○) NaOH-treated (H-type).

from alcoholic solutions, however, gave L-type isotherm, a representative flatwise (horizontal to the surface) monodisperse followed by multilayer

formation with ionic micellisation. The start of plateau (knee) in the isotherms indicates monolayer formation while the end of the plateau signifies the completion of monolayer. The second rise in adsorption against solution concentration indicates further build-up of multilayers. Similar adsorption was observed in an earlier investigation on adsorption of methyl violet on some oxide surfaces^a. The silica surface treated with sodium hydroxide solution exhibited much diminished adsorption activity, limited to only monolayer formation. The monolayer adsorption capacity from alcoholic solution ($X_m = 1.6 \text{ mg dm}^{-3} \text{ g}^{-1}$) is comparable with that from basic solution ($X_m = 1.8 \text{ mg dm}^{-3} \text{ g}^{-1}$). Both are adsorbed horizontal to the surface, occupying the same area of the surface, with the difference that the adsorption from alcoholic solution is not restricted to monolayer and leads to further build-up of multilayer and/or ionic micelles formation. Adsorption from aqueous solution gives monolayer capacity which is almost four times higher ($X_m = 7.0 \text{ mg dm}^{-3} \text{ g}^{-1}$) than observed from basic and alcoholic solutions. This is interpreted as follows. Silica being slightly soluble in water forms silicic acid^b and consequently the acidity on the silica surface is increased and therefore the adsorption

TABLE 1—MONOLAYER ADSORPTION CAPACITY (X_m) OF RHODAMINE B, FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT FOR MONOLAYER (k') AND FOR MULTILAYER (k'') ADSORPTION

Solvent	X_m $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{ g}^{-1}$	k' s^{-1}	k'' s^{-1}	k'/k''
Water	7.0	3.1×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-6}	11
Alcohol	1.6	9.4×10^{-6}	1.4×10^{-6}	7
NaOH	1.8	—	—	—

Fig. 3. First order kinetic plots of rhodamine B adsorbed from: (●) aqueous, (●) alcoholic, and (○) NaOH-treated silica gel.

affinity is increased for basic dye rhodamine B from aqueous solution. Furthermore, adsorption from aqueous solution is end-on, oriented vertical to the surface and therefore covers less exposed surface than that observed in adsorption from basic and alcoholic solutions, wherein adsorption is flatwise. Therefore, higher monolayer adsorption capacity from aqueous solution is anticipated. The X_m values (Table 1) reveal that end-on adsorption of rhodamine B species occupies an area which is about four times greater than that occupied by flatwise adsorbed species.

The kinetics of the processes occurring at the silica-solution interface is of prime importance in understanding the interfacial phenomena. The results show that adsorption at first is fast, approaches steadily towards the equilibrium concentration, and the equilibrium is attained at fairly short time period (30 min). The first order kinetic

plots (Fig. 3) suggest involvement of two processes (except for adsorption from basic solution) at the solid-solution interface; one responsible for fast adsorption, while the other leading to slow multilayer and/or ionic micelles formation. This idea is further supported from the values of the first order rate constants for both the processes (Table 1). The results suggest that the monolayer adsorption is far more favoured process as compared to the multilayer and/or micellisation process.

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